

Optimisation of optics for direct fringe detection

L. Lindegren (30 June 1997)

1 Introduction

The astrometric precision is evaluated as function of main optical and detector parameters such as focal length, baseline and pixel size. The purpose is to estimate the optimum baselength and focal length for given pixel size.

The theoretical expressions for the parallax precision derived in a previous note (*Astrometric precision for direct fringe detection (v1)*, 15 April 1997) are used. However, more realistic assumptions are made concerning the CCD quantum efficiency and stellar fluxes. The optimisation puts emphasis on red stars.

2 Assumptions

A very important design parameter is the affordable size of the (interferometric) field of view, or rather the part of the field that can be covered with CCD detectors for astrometry. Since the focal length is considered a free parameter, there is no *a priori* fixed relation between the detector area and the detector solid angle. Both are in practice limited by design considerations which are beyond the scope of this exercise. The detector area (H) is limited by the linear space available for the focal plane, by the packing density of the chips, and perhaps by power and cooling factors. The detector solid angle (Ω) is limited by the maximum field in which diffraction limited performance can be achieved, by vignetting, etc.

For this study we assume a maximum detector area of $H_{\max} = 0.5 \text{ m}^2$ per interferometer and a maximum detector solid angle of $\Omega_{\max} = 1 \text{ deg}^2$. These numbers define a critical focal length, $F_0 = (H_{\max}/\Omega_{\max})^{1/2} \simeq 40 \text{ m}$, such that the performance is limited by $\Omega_{\max}$ for $F < F_0$ and by $H_{\max}$ for $F > F_0$.

Other input parameters are shown in Table 1. The upper part of the table gives the fixed parameters, the lower part the parameters subject to optimisation and their ranges. Linear pixel widths of $F\Delta\xi = 3.5, 5, 7$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$ are considered, and in each case the astrometric standard error is minimised with respect to interferometer baselength B and focal length F .

The assumed quantum efficiency is shown in Figure 1. It is taken to be the same for all pixel sizes, although the real response may be considerably reduced for small pixels, especially in the red.

Optimisation is made for an unreddened K3 giant star of magnitude $V = 15$. For comparison, precision estimates are also calculated for a star of spectral type A0V (again at $V = 15$), and for a strongly reddened K3III star (at $V = 20, A_V = 5 \text{ mag}$). The flux distributions for the three object types, normalised to $V = 0$, are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Assumed quantum efficiency for CCD detectors. The curve is for a thinned CCD with $13.5 \mu\text{m}$ pixel width. The same curve is used for all pixel width. (S. Röser, fax 6/6/97.)

Figure 2. Assumed monochromatic fluxes normalised to magnitude $V = 0$. (Adapted from Gunn & Stryker, ApJS 52, 121, 1983.)

Table 1. Parameters used for the optimisation of astrometric precision

Parameter	Value(s)	Meaning
<i>Fixed parameters:</i>		
L_{eff}	0.8×5 years	effective mission length
N_i	2	number of interferometers
D	0.6 m (circular)	pupil size
Ω_{max}	0.000305 sr (1 deg ²)	maximum detector solid angle per interferometer
H_{max}	0.5 m ²	maximum detector area per interferometer
$F\Delta\eta$	50 μm	pixel height (normal to scan)
r	5	RMS read-out noise
$N_\xi F\Delta\xi$	0.05 m	linear size of CCD chip (along scan)
T_λ	0.8	total optical transmittance
Q_λ	Figure 1	quantum efficiency
ω	120 arcsec s ⁻¹	spin rate
G	2.0	geometric parallax factor
k	0.5	numerical constant in CR approximation
V	15 mag	magnitude of target star
f_λ	K3III ($A_V = 0$)	flux distribution (cf. Figure 2)
V_b	20 mag	sky brightness (per arcsec ²)
$(V-I)_b$	2.0	colour index of sky
<i>Parameter ranges considered in the optimisation:</i>		
$F\Delta\xi$	3.5 ... 10 μm	pixel width (along scan)
B	0.6 ... 2.4 m	interferometer baselength
F	15 ... 100 m	(effective) focal length

3 Precision versus B and F

Figure 3 shows the estimated standard error in parallax, as function of B and F , for a fixed linear pixel width of 10 μm . For comparison the precision was also calculated for the case of incoherent detection, i.e. where only the Airy envelope of the diffraction image is used. Formally this case is obtained in the limit of infinite baselength; actually it was computed for $B = 10$ m.

The diagram shows several interesting features. It is seen how the interferometer improves the precision roughly by a factor of two, compared with the incoherent case ($B = \infty$), as the focal length becomes sufficient to resolve the fringes. As a rule of thumb, for a pixel size of 10 μm , we need a focal length of at least 20–25 times the baselength in order to benefit from the interferometric resolution. This factor scales with the linear pixel width.

For a fixed detector solid angle and increasing focal length the curves would eventually reach a constant level inversely proportional to the baselength. However, this never happens in Figure 3 because the limitation in detector area sets in at $F = 40$ m. From that point, if the fringes are well resolved, the standard error is instead directly proportional to the focal length. As a result, the optimum focal length equals the critical value (40 m), at a baselength of about 1 m. The corresponding interferogram is in Figure 4.

Figures 5–10 are for successively smaller pixel widths of 7, 5 and 3.5 μm . The optimum focal length is $F = 40$ m in every case, and the optimum baselength is, respectively, $B = 1.5, 1.8$ and 2.4 m. As a rule of thumb, $B_{\text{opt}} \simeq (10 \text{ m})/(\text{pixel width in } \mu\text{m})$.

The circumstance that $F_{\text{opt}} = 40$ m in all the cases studied is of course related to the choice of maximum detector area (H_{max}) and maximum detector solid angle (Ω_{max}). Indeed, if these could be determined independently of other considerations (which in practice is not possible), we would find that $F_{\text{opt}} = (H_{\text{max}}/\Omega_{\text{max}})^{1/2}$ for a rather wide range of other parameters. Thus, the optimum focal length is the maximum value compatible with a given maximum angular field of view. The key point seems to be that it is generally not useful to increase the focal length at the expense of the angular field, as long as the fringes are reasonably resolved.

4 Choice of pixel width

In comparing the performances of the different pixel widths it must be recalled that there may be a heavy penalty in quantum efficiency and readout noise when going to smaller pixels. This may partly (or wholly?) offset the formal gain in precision shown in Figures 3, 5, 7 and 9. However, the loss may not be so big when going from 10 to 7 μm as for the smaller pixels, and since 7 μm already permits a relatively comfortable baselength of about 1.5 m, this appears to be a reasonable compromise (lacking more detailed data for such detectors).

5 Precision versus magnitude and colour

For pixel width 7 μm , focal length $F = 40$ m, and baselength $B = 1.5$ m we obtain the astrometric precision in Table 2.

Table 2. Estimated standard error in parallax (σ_a , in μas) versus magnitude for unreddened A and K stars, and for a strongly reddened K star.

V	A0V ($A_V = 0$)	K3III ($A_V = 0$)	K3III ($A_V = 5$)
15	10.9	9.2	4.7
16	17.3	14.6	7.5
17	27.8	23.4	11.9
18	45.3	38.2	19.0
19	77.0	64.5	30.8
20	141	117	51.4
21	283	233	91.2

Figure 3. Parallax accuracy versus focal length (F) and baselengths $B = 0.6$ (0.3) 2.4 m, for a pixel width of $10 \mu\text{m}$. See Table 1 for other parameters.

Figure 4. Interferogram for pixel width $10 \mu\text{m}$, $F = 40 \text{ m}$, $B = 0.9 \text{ m}$. The dots show the eight times oversampled curve.

Figure 5. Parallax accuracy versus focal length (F) and baselengths $B = 0.6$ (0.3) 2.4 m, for a pixel width of $7 \mu\text{m}$. See Table 1 for other parameters.

Figure 6. Interferogram for pixel width $7 \mu\text{m}$, $F = 40$ m, $B = 1.5$ m. The dots show the eight times oversampled curve.

Figure 7. Parallax accuracy versus focal length (F) and baselengths $B = 0.6$ (0.3) 2.4 m , for a pixel width of $5 \mu\text{m}$. See Table 1 for other parameters.

Figure 8. Interferogram for pixel width $5 \mu\text{m}$, $F = 40 \text{ m}$, $B = 1.8 \text{ m}$. The dots show the eight times oversampled curve.

Figure 9. Parallax accuracy versus focal length (F) and baselengths $B = 0.6$ (0.3) 2.4 m, for a pixel width of $3.5 \mu\text{m}$. See Table 1 for other parameters.

Figure 10. Interferogram for pixel width $3.5 \mu\text{m}$, $F = 40 \text{ m}$, $B = 2.4 \text{ m}$. The dots show the eight times oversampled curve.

6 Fringe dispersion

The potential gain in precision from fringe dispersion was evaluated by considering a pixel height of $30 \mu\text{m}$ and a linear dispersion of 50 nm/pixel . The somewhat reduced pixel height corresponds to about 0.7 times the FWHM of the Airy disk. The precision was evaluated separately for each of the 15 wavelength bands 300–350 nm, 350–400 nm, ... 1000–1050 nm, and the total precision was estimated as $(\sum_{i=1}^{15} \sigma_i^{-2})^{-1/2}$. Results are shown in Table 3. To avoid the loss of precision at $V = 20$ a readout noise less than $3 e^-$ RMS is required.

Note that this calculation does not take into account image overlapping, smearing of the spectrum along the dispersion, and a number of other factors affecting the fringe dispersion in a negative way. On the other hand, if fringe dispersion is not used some other method is needed to obtain multi-colour photometry, most likely at the expense of the astrometrically useful field; this factor was not included either. On the whole, the gain from using fringe dispersion is rather modest and probably absent for the faint stars.

Table 3. Estimated standard error in parallax without and with fringe dispersion (FD).

Case	Without FD	With FD	Change in σ
A0V, $V = 15$, $A_V = 0$	10.9	8.7	−20%
K3III, $V = 15$, $A_V = 0$	9.2	7.6	−18%
K3III, $V = 20$, $A_V = 5$	51.4	64.8	+26%

7 Conclusions

Within a rather wide range of other parameters the optimum focal length is mainly governed by the achievable linear and angular field size. With reasonable assumptions it may be about 40 m. A pixel width less than $10 \mu\text{m}$ is required, but it does not have to be extremely small. For instance, a pixel size of $7 \mu\text{m}$ is compatible with a baselength of 1.5 m, while longer baselines require smaller pixels.

The red sensitivity and the improved fringe visibility with wavelength gives very favourable performance for strongly reddened objects.

The benefit of fringe dispersion in terms of potential astrometric accuracy is modest for bright stars, and probably absent for faint stars.